

DETERMINING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SEISMIC BARRIERS BY CHANGING THEIR HEIGHT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13623022>

Abstract. *In the article, the impact of seismic surface waves on the building was determined using the Plaxis 3D software complex using the Finite Element method. The highest displacement amplitudes at each point are determined. Seismic barriers with a height of 1 meter, 3 meters, 5 meters, and 7 meters are modeled, and their effectiveness by reducing seismic surface waves is studied and a comparative comparison is made.*

Keywords: *building, seismic surface waves, finite element method, theory of elasticity, seismic barrier.*

Introduction

Seismic barriers are crucial for mitigating damage caused by natural disasters, particularly earthquakes. These barriers protect buildings and infrastructure from seismic activity, thereby safeguarding human lives. The primary function of seismic barriers is to absorb, reflect, or dissipate seismic energy, reducing the damage to the structural integrity of buildings and infrastructure.

Seismic surface waves can move through the ground and cause significant damage to structures. Seismic barriers play an important role, especially in high seismic activity areas. These barriers can be constructed using various materials and technologies, and their effectiveness depends on factors such as height, material quality, and construction methods. The performance of seismic barriers is largely influenced by their height, materials, and construction techniques. Height, for example, directly affects a barrier's ability to reflect or dissipate seismic waves, making it essential to evaluate properly and optimize this factor.

Research Materials and Methodology

This study aims to analyze the effectiveness of seismic barriers by varying their height to explore possibilities for improving their performance and enhancing seismic safety. The objective is to evaluate how changing the height of seismic barriers affects their effectiveness and to determine the optimal height. Through this analysis, we will investigate how barriers of different heights influence seismic waves and perform a comparative assessment.

The study focuses on determining how the placement of seismic barriers affects their ability to mitigate the impact of Rayleigh surface waves on buildings. This involves evaluating and comparing the performance of seismic barriers at different heights.

To solve the problem numerically, a finite model with dimensions of 200 m in length, 100 m in width, and 50 m in depth was selected. In the problem, groundwater is assumed to be at a depth of 20 m. The building is 24 m in length, 24 m in width, and 14.75 m in height, with a floor height of 3.3 m, and the basement part of the building is located at a depth of 3 m. The first layer of soil is modeled as 5 meters of loamy sand (Loam), and the second layer is modeled as 45 meters of gravelly soil (Pebble) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Discretization of the soil model and residential building into finite elements.

Figure 2. Seismic Barriers of Annular Shape with Thickness of 1 Meter and Heights of 1, 3, 5, and 7 Meters

The circular vertical seismic barrier is positioned 28 meters from the center of the building, with a thickness of 1 meter and a height of 1, 3, 5 and 7 meters (Figure 2).

In this problem, an infinite semi-space is replaced by a finite domain. The following conditions are imposed at the boundaries to ensure the waves approach infinity [1,2,3].

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \sigma_x = a\rho V_p \dot{u} \\ \tau_{yz} = b\rho V_s \dot{v} \\ \tau_{zy} = b\rho V_s \dot{w} \end{array} \right\} \left. \begin{array}{l} \sigma_y = a\rho V_p \dot{v} \\ \tau_{xz} = b\rho V_s \dot{w} \\ \tau_{zx} = b\rho V_s \dot{u} \end{array} \right\} \left. \begin{array}{l} \sigma_z = a\rho V_p \dot{w} \\ \tau_{xy} = b\rho V_s \dot{u} \\ \tau_{yx} = b\rho V_s \dot{v} \end{array} \right\} \quad (1)$$

The research domain is divided into 47,109 finite elements and 86,147 nodes. The shapes of the finite elements are chosen as irregular tetrahedra (Figure 1).

The order of the system of differential equations of motion is $86,147 \times 3 = 258,441$. The kinematic relations can be formulated as follows [1,2,3]:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{u} \quad (2)$$

L^T - Transposed differential operator

$$\mathbf{L}^T = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \\ \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

In general, each element material may have an initial deformation due to temperature changes, expansion, or crystallization [1,2,3]. If we denote this deformation by $\{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_0\}$, the stress is determined by the difference between the current deformation and the initial deformation. Additionally, it is convenient to consider that there might be residual stress that can be measured

at the time of observation [1,2,3]. This stress is added to the general expression for stress. When considering the material of the body as elastic, the relationship between stress and deformation is linear [1,2,3]:

$$\{\sigma\} = [D]({\{\varepsilon\}} - {\{\varepsilon_0\}}) + {\{\sigma_0\}} \quad (4)$$

Here, $[D]$ is the elasticity matrix representing the material properties.

In the case of plane stress, three components of stress corresponding to deformation are written as follows [1,2,3]:

$$\{\sigma\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}$$

The matrix $[D]$ is determined from the following relationship between stress and deformation:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_x - (\varepsilon_x)_0 &= \frac{1}{E} \sigma_x - \frac{\nu}{E} \sigma_y; & \varepsilon_y - (\varepsilon_y)_0 &= -\frac{\nu}{E} \sigma_x + \frac{1}{E} \sigma_y; \\ \gamma_{xy} - (\gamma_{xy})_0 &= \frac{2 + (1 + \nu)}{E} \tau_{xy}; \end{aligned}$$

From this:

$$[D] = \frac{E}{1 - \nu^2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \nu & 0 \\ \nu & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1 - \nu}{2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The system of differential equations for the motion of a mechanical system subjected to dynamic loads is expressed as follows [1,3]:

$$M\ddot{u} + C\dot{u} + Ku = F \quad (6)$$

Here, M is the mass matrix, C is the damping matrix, K is the stiffness matrix, and F is the dynamic load vector. u is the displacement vector, \dot{u} is the velocity vector, and \ddot{u} is the acceleration vector, which are considered continuous functions of time [2,3].

In the numerical formulation of dynamic problems, the time iteration formulation is a crucial factor for the stability and accuracy of the computer processing [3].

We adopt the time iteration coefficients for the Newmark method $\alpha = 0.25$ and $\beta = 0.5$ [2,3]. The properties of the soil, building, and seismic barrier are provided in Table 1 [2,3].

Table 1

Parameter	Unit of measure	Designation	Name of the soil	
			Loam	Pebble
General Properties of the Soil				
Model type	–	–	Liner elastic	Liner elastic
Soil parameter	–	–	Dried	Dried
The specific gravity of the upper layer of the soil under the influence of groundwater	kN/m ³	γ_{unsat}	16	19
The specific gravity of the bottom layer of the soil under the influence of groundwater	kN/m ³	γ_{sat}	17	20.5
Initial porosity coefficient	–	e_{init}	0.5	0.5

Young's modulus	kN/m ²	E	50000	90000
Poisson's ratio	—	ν	0.35	0.3
Longitudinal wave speed	m/s	V_P	218.4	250.1
Transverse wavelength	m/s	V_S	104.9	133.7
General Properties of the Building				
Model Type	—	—	Elastic	
Elasticity Modulus	kN/m ²	E	27500000	
Poisson's Ratio	—	ν	0.2	
Density	kN/m ³	γ	24	
General Properties of the Barrier				
Model Type	—	—	Elastic	
Elasticity Modulus	kN/m ²	E	1000	
Poisson's Ratio	—	ν	0.3	
Density	kN/m ³	γ	12	

To determine and compare the impact of seismic surface waves on the building, 9 observation points per floor, totaling 54 points, were designated for the building (Figure 5) [3].

Figure 3. Observation Points

The propagation of seismic surface waves was generated using a harmonic force. The phase of the harmonic force is 0, with an amplitude of 1 and a frequency of 10 Hz, and a duration of 5 seconds (Figure 6) [3].

Figure 4. Harmonic Force Law

When seismic surface waves impact the building, the maximum amplitude values of u_z at the predesignated observation points in the building were determined and tabulated (Table 2).

To assess the reduction of seismic surface waves affecting the building and the advantages of varying the height of seismic barriers, seismic barriers with heights of 1, 3, 5, and 7 meters were modeled. The maximum amplitudes of displacement along the building's longitudinal axis at specified points (Table 2) were analyzed comparatively.

Figure 5. Process of Seismic Surface Waves Affecting the Building

Table 2

№	Observation Points	Coordinates (x, y, z)	No barrier Displacement (mm)	Barrier			
				1 meter	3 meter	5 meter	7 meter
				Displacement (mm)	Displacement (mm)	Displacement (mm)	Displacement (mm)
The ground part of the building	1	100, 38, -3	1,527	1,702	1,305	1,266	1,096
	2	100, 50, -3	1,518	1,662	1,291	1,220	1,128
	3	100, 62, -3	1,455	1,626	1,242	1,242	1,113
	4	112, 38, -3	0,912	0,633	0,503	0,410	0,360
	5	112, 50, -3	0,825	0,655	0,467	0,398	0,367
	6	112, 62, -3	0,811	0,705	0,516	0,402	0,366
	7	124, 38, -3	0,722	0,744	0,630	0,689	0,643
	8	124, 50, -3	0,772	0,841	0,678	0,674	0,657
	9	124, 62, -3	0,859	0,937	0,779	0,626	0,641
1st floor	10	100, 38, 0,75	1,539	1,712	1,312	1,276	1,107
	11	100, 50, 0,75	1,535	1,679	1,301	1,233	1,138
	12	100, 62, 0,75	1,465	1,641	1,254	1,248	1,121
	13	112, 38, 0,75	0,915	0,628	0,505	0,405	0,357
	14	112, 50, 0,75	0,819	0,651	0,465	0,396	0,363
	15	112, 62, 0,75	0,809	0,700	0,513	0,399	0,364
	16	124, 38, 0,75	0,729	0,748	0,633	0,692	0,644
	17	124, 50, 0,75	0,775	0,843	0,681	0,675	0,655
	18	124, 62, 0,75	0,867	0,937	0,779	0,630	0,642
2nd floor	19	100, 38, 4,05	1,683	1,759	1,345	1,321	1,159
	20	100, 50, 4,05	1,670	1,744	1,344	1,289	1,182
	21	100, 62, 4,05	1,608	1,724	1,320	1,293	1,165

	22	112, 38, 4,05	0,933	0,622	0,554	0,402	0,357
	23	112, 50, 4,05	0,797	0,641	0,458	0,390	0,354
	24	112, 62, 4,05	0,797	0,694	0,508	0,398	0,381
	25	124, 38, 4,05	0,758	0,765	0,633	0,698	0,640
	26	124, 50, 4,05	0,800	0,853	0,692	0,679	0,651
	27	124, 62, 4,05	0,903	0,939	0,782	0,642	0,649
	3rd floor	28	100, 38, 7,35	1,822	1,790	1,367	1,352
29		100, 50, 7,35	1,802	1,782	1,371	1,325	1,210
30		100, 62, 7,35	1,742	1,777	1,362	1,325	1,195
31		112, 38, 7,35	0,950	0,617	0,587	0,399	0,357
32		112, 50, 7,35	0,785	0,637	0,455	0,387	0,349
33		112, 62, 7,35	0,790	0,690	0,505	0,398	0,394
34		124, 38, 7,35	0,782	0,778	0,632	0,703	0,639
35		124, 50, 7,35	0,819	0,862	0,701	0,683	0,650
36		124, 62, 7,35	0,938	0,943	0,786	0,650	0,654
4th floor	37	100, 38, 10,65	1,897	1,807	1,380	1,370	1,214
	38	100, 50, 10,65	1,864	1,801	1,385	1,343	1,226
	39	100, 62, 10,65	1,812	1,804	1,384	1,343	1,212
	40	112, 38, 10,65	0,959	0,615	0,604	0,397	0,356
	41	112, 50, 10,65	0,782	0,635	0,454	0,386	0,346
	42	112, 62, 10,65	0,787	0,688	0,503	0,398	0,399
	43	124, 38, 10,65	0,795	0,786	0,633	0,707	0,640
	44	124, 50, 10,65	0,828	0,868	0,706	0,686	0,651
	45	124, 62, 10,65	0,960	0,947	0,790	0,654	0,657
Top Part of the Building	46	100, 38, 13,95	1,919	1,812	1,384	1,376	1,220
	47	100, 50, 13,95	1,878	1,806	1,389	1,348	1,230
	48	100, 62, 13,95	1,832	1,812	1,391	1,348	1,217
	49	112, 38, 13,95	0,960	0,614	0,607	0,396	0,355

50	112, 50, 13,95	0,781	0,634	0,454	0,386	0,346
51	112, 62, 13,95	0,786	0,687	0,502	0,397	0,400
52	124, 38, 13,95	0,800	0,789	0,633	0,709	0,640
53	124, 50, 13,95	0,832	0,871	0,709	0,687	0,652
54	124, 62, 13,95	0,966	0,949	0,792	0,655	0,641

Figure 8. Contrastive Comparison Graph of Displacement at Observation Point 54

In Figure 8, at the 54th observation point of the building without any surrounding barriers, the maximum displacement of the seismic surface wave along the u_z axis is $u_{zmax}=0,966$ mm. For the building with a seismic barrier of 1 meter height, $u_{zmax}=0,949$ mm; for the building with a seismic barrier of 3 meters height, $u_{zmax}=0,792$ mm; for the building with a seismic barrier of 5 meters height, $u_{zmax}=0,655$ mm; and for the building with a seismic barrier of 7 meters height, $u_{zmax}=0,641$ mm.

Compared to the building without any surrounding barriers, the effectiveness of the seismic barriers is recorded as 1.79% for the 1-meter height barrier, 18.06% - for the 3-meter height barrier, 32.21% - for the 5-meter height barrier, and 33.66% - for the 7-meter height barrier.

Figure 9. Contrastive Comparison Graph of Velocity at Observation Point 54

In Figure 9, the maximum value of the velocity of the seismic surface wave along the v_z axis at observation point 54 of the building without any obstacles around it is $v_{zmax}=6,50$ cm/s, in the building with a 1-meter-high seismic barrier $v_{zmax}=4,59$ cm/s, $v_{zmax}=4,19$ cm/s in a building with a 3-meter-high seismic barrier, $v_{zmax}=2,06$ cm/s in a building with a 5-meter-high seismic barrier, a 7-meter-high seismic barrier $v_{zmax}=1,82$ cm/s in a densely located building. In a contrastive comparison, the speed at observation point 54 of a building with a 1-meter-high seismic barrier is 29.38% compared to a building without any barriers around the building, 35.53% in a building with a 3-meter-high seismic barrier, and 68.31% in the building with a 5-meter-high seismic barrier, and 72.00% in the building with a 7-meter high seismic barrier.

Figure 10. Contrastive Comparison Graph of Acceleration at Observation Point 54

In Figure 10, at observation point 54 of a building with no barriers around it, the maximum acceleration of the seismic surface wave along the a_z axis is $a_{zmax}=54,49$ cm/s². For a building with a 1-meter-high seismic barrier, $a_{zmax}=45,65$ cm/s²; with a 3-meter-high barrier, $a_{zmax}=38,29$ cm/s²; with a 5-meter-high barrier, $a_{zmax}=24,00$ cm/s²; and with a 7-meter-high barrier, $a_{zmax}=16,83$ cm/s². In comparison, the effectiveness of the seismic barriers is noted as follows: a 1-meter-high barrier reduces the acceleration by 16.22%, a 3-meter-high barrier - by 29.73%, a 5-meter-high barrier - by 55.95%, and a 7-meter-high barrier - by 69.11% relative to the building with no barriers.

To reduce the impact of seismic surface waves on the building, a circular seismic barrier with a radius of 28 meters and a thickness of 1 meter was modeled with heights of 1, 3, 5, and 7 meters to examine the process of reducing seismic surface waves.

Conclusion:

Based on the obtained results and the graphics in the figures, it is evident that compared to a building with no barriers around it, the building with a seismic barrier of 1 meter height, located at the center of the building with a radius of 28 meters and a thickness of 1 meter, shows an average reduction in displacement of 3.15%, velocity of 37.98%, and acceleration of 21.09%. For a building with a seismic barrier of 3 meters height, the average reductions are 24.05% in displacement, 56.53% in velocity, and 50.13% in acceleration. For a seismic barrier of 5 meters height, the reductions are 29.26% in displacement, 63.93% in velocity, and 51.58% in acceleration. For a seismic barrier of 7 meters height, the reductions are 34.94% in displacement, 66.13% in

velocity, and 62.66% in acceleration. This indicates a significant decrease in the oscillation level of seismic surface waves.

According to this analysis, it is clear that the effectiveness of seismic barriers in reducing the impact of seismic surface waves is dependent on the height of the barriers. The results suggest that increasing the height of seismic barriers can significantly reduce the level of seismic surface wave oscillations. As the height of the seismic barrier increases, a decrease in displacement, velocity, and acceleration is observed. This implies that taller seismic barriers are more effective in resisting and reducing the spread of surface waves, thus minimizing damage to the building. The modeling results indicate that a seismic barrier with a height of 7 meters is most effective in reducing the oscillation of surface waves. In summary, increasing the height of seismic barriers results in a significant reduction in the impact of seismic surface waves on the building, highlighting its importance in enhancing seismic safety. Utilizing such seismic barriers in construction, especially in highly seismically active areas, can significantly improve the safety of buildings.

REFERENCES

1. Yuldashev, S. S., & Abdunazarov, A. S. (2023). BINOGA TA'SIR ETAYOTGAN SEYSMIK SIRT TO 'LQINLARNI ANIQLASH VA SEYSMIK TO'SIQ (PENOPOLIURETAN) YORDAMIDA KAMAYTIRISH: BINOGA TA'SIR ETAYOTGAN SEYSMIK SIRT TO 'LQINLARNI ANIQLASH VA SEYSMIK TO'SIQ (PENOPOLIURETAN) YORDAMIDA KAMAYTIRISH.
2. Sayfitdinovich, Y. S., & Shamsuddin o'g'li, A. A. (2023). BINOGA TA'SIR ETAYOTGAN SEYSMIK SIRT TO 'LQINLARINING GRUNT XUSUSIYATIGA BOG'LIQLIGI: BINOGA TA'SIR ETAYOTGAN SEYSMIK SIRT TO 'LQINLARINING GRUNT XUSUSIYATIGA BOG 'LIQLIGI.
3. Sayfitdinovich, Y. S., Latifovich, A. X., Shamsuddin o'g'li, A. A., Gulmira, Y., & Akbarovich, X. X. (2023). YER OSTI SUVLARI SATHINING SEYSMIK SIRT TO'LQINLARI TARQALISHIGA TA'SIRI: YER OSTI SUVLARI SATHINING SEYSMIK SIRT TO 'LQINLARI TARQALISHIGA TA'SIRI.